

Synthesis of Azo-Benzene Nitrogen Mustards

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As part of our programme for the search of potential anti-tumour compounds a series of azo-benzene nitrogen mustards have been synthesised by coupling of N,N-bis-(2-haloethyl) anilines with various diazotised sulfa drugs.

In all twenty mustards of the above type have been prepared from 4-N,N-bis-(2-chloroethyl) aniline and 4-N,N-bis-(2-bromoethyl) aniline and a diazotised (a) sulfanilamide, (b) sulfathiazole, (c) sulfaguanidine, (d) sulfadimidine, (e) sulfadiazine, (f) sulfasomidine, (g) sulfafurazole, (h) sulfapyridine, (i) sulfamethoxy pyridazine, (j) sulfaphenazole.

TABLE 1

	R	X	M.P. °C*	Method	Yield (%)	Formula
1.	-H	Cl	163-4	A	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl ₂
2.	2-thiazolyl	Cl	184-5	A	45	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ S ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂
3.	guanidyl	Cl	175	B	58	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ SO ₂ Cl ₂
4.	4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidyl	Cl	174	A	27	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ SO ₂ Cl ₂
5.	2-Pyrimidyl	Cl	210-15	B	25	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ SO ₂ Cl ₂
6.	2,6-dimethyl-4-pyrimidyl	Cl	174	A	27	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ SO ₂ Cl ₂
7.	3,4-dimethyl-5-iso-oxazolyl	Cl	156-7	B	28	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₆ SO ₃ Cl ₂
8.	2-pyridyl	Cl	172	A	10	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ SO ₂ Cl ₂
9.	6-methoxy-3-pyridazyl	Cl	160	A	10	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ SO ₃ Cl ₂
10.	1-phenyl-5-pyrazolyl	Cl	175d	A	10	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₆ SO ₂ Cl ₂
11.	-H	Br	167	A	7	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ SO ₂ Br ₂
12.	2-thiazolyl	Br	178	A	17	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ S ₂ O ₂ Br ₂
13.	guanidyl	Br	77-8	B	16	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ SO ₂ Br ₂
14.	4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidyl	Br	188	A	18	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ SO ₂ Br ₂
15.	2-pyrimidyl	Br	260	B	9	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ SO ₂ Br ₂
16.	2,6-dimethyl-4-pyrimidyl	Br	164-5	A	6	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ SO ₂ Br ₂
17.	3,4-dimethyl-5-iso-oxazolyl	Br	101	B	10	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₆ SO ₃ Br ₂
18.	2-pyridyl	Br	174	A	8	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ SO ₂ Br ₂
19.	1-phenyl-5-pyrazolyl	Br	130-2	A	10	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₆ SO ₂ Br ₂
20.	-H	H	190	A	69	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ SO ₂

* All the m.ps. are uncorrected.

EXPERIMENTAL

N,N-bis-(2-chloroethyl) aniline was prepared by the method of Robinson and Watts¹. N,N-bis-(2-bromoethyl) aniline was prepared as follows :

A mixture of the 4-N,N-bis-(2-chloroethyl) aniline (13.08 g), lithium bromide (20 g) and methyl isobutylketone (225 ml.) was refluxed with stirring for 6 hr. The mixture was then concentrated to a slurry and poured into water to give the bromo-compound. It was recrystallised from petroleum ether (40°-60°). Yield (70%); m.p. 53°-4°, lit.² 53°-5°.

Coupling of 4-N,N-bis-(2-haloethyl) anilines with diazotised sulfa drugs : A solution of (0.01 mole) appropriate sulfa drug in 90 ml acetic acid (50%, Method A) or hydrochloric acid (3 ml) and water (15 ml) (Method B) was cooled below 0° and diazotised by the addition of (0.01 mole) sodium nitrite in water (6 ml) under vigorous stirring. After one hour, the diazonium salt was added to a cold solution (5°-10°) of the appropriate nitrogen mustard (0.01 mole) in ethanol (minimum amount) under stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 12 hr at 0°; the dye which separated was then filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. The yields, m.ps. and analyses of the different azo compounds are recorded in Table I.

Found (%)	Required (%)	Found (%)	Required (%)
C : 48.00	C : 47.88	C : 39.68	C : 39.18
H : 4.66	H : 4.48	H : 3.96	H : 3.67
N : 13.68	N : 13.96	N : 11.70	N : 11.42
N : 14.04	N : 14.46	N : 12.61	N : 12.21
N : 18.64	N : 18.96	C : 39.06	C : 38.54
N : 15.99	N : 16.56	H : 4.11	H : 3.75
C : 50.19	C : 50.10	N : 15.95	N : 15.78
H : 4.56	H : 4.17	N : 13.61	N : 14.09
N : 17.31	N : 17.53	N : 14.25	N : 14.78
N : 16.65	N : 16.56	C : 44.77	C : 44.29
N : 13.81	N : 14.11	H : 4.42	H : 4.02
N : 14.18	N : 14.64	N : 13.60	N : 14.09
N : 16.16	N : 16.56	N : 12.34	N : 11.95
C : 55.61	C : 55.24	C : 44.28	C : 44.44
H : 4.26	H : 4.41	H : 4.09	H : 3.70
N : 15.88	N : 15.46	N : 12.23	N : 12.34
		N : 12.94	N : 13.28
		C : 58.17	C : 57.83
		H : 6.03	H : 6.02
		N : 16.61	N : 16.86

REFERENCES

1. R. Robinson and J. S. Watts, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1536.
2. W. C. J. Ross, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 183.